

Prediction of Parkinson's Disease Using Machine Learning

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Abstract— One of the most deadly disorders is Parkinson's disease. As a result, detecting it at an earlier stage may assist to prevent or mitigate the symptoms. By comparing different machine learning algorithms, such as logistic regression, decision tree, closest neighbour, and some matching techniques, machine learning classification algorithms are used to predict whether a person has Parkinson's disease or not. "Established" learning is when we combine numerous models to try to increase accuracy. Parkinson's disease is a degenerative neurological disorder that causes tremors, stiffness, and trouble walking, balancing, and regulating one's movements.. Parkinson's disease symptoms typically begin gradually and gets worse over time.

Keywords— machine learning, support vector machine, XGBoost.

I. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a neurological disorder in which dopamine (di-ortho-phenyl-alanine)-containing cells in the substantia nigra die. There is no test that can accurately differentiate Parkinson's disease from other disorders that have comparable clinical symptoms. The diagnosis is mostly clinical and it is based on that patient's medical history and the physical examination. Parkinson's illness is named after the British neurologist who, in 1817, published the first book about the disorder, which established it as a distinct entity. "The Shaking Palsy," or "paralysis agitans," was Parkinson's term for it. Tremors were referred to as "agitans" in his day. Although "palsy" meant "weakness" and "paralysis" means "numbness," the disorder was named "weakness and tremor disorder," which isn't quite true, as we'll see. It's a long-term, progressive neurodegenerative illness with both motor and non-motor symptoms. As non-motor symptoms suggest neuroinflammation in non-dopaminergic areas, motor symptoms in Parkinson's disease are connected to the loss of striatal dopaminergic neurons. The term "parkinsonism" used to denote a situation which is similar to parkinson's disease.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

A. M. Abdar and M. Zomorodi-Moghadam (M. Abdar and M. Zomorodi-Moghadam) (M. Abdar and M. Zomorodi-Moghadam) "Using Classification Algorithms, on the Impact on Patients Gender on Parkinson's Disease" SVM and Bayesian Networks were employed in this system to classify data based on the patient's gender. SVM accuracy was 90.98 percent, whereas Bayesian network accuracy was 88.62

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6874127

ISBN: 978-93-5607-317-3@2022 MCA, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

percent. This test demonstrated that the SVM algorithm was capable of correctly identifying a PD patient's gender.

B. Sahoo et al. (2012) [4] published a study that used data mining approaches to predict Parkinson's disease. Decision stump, Logistic Regression, and Sequential Minimization Optimization were the three approaches employed. According to the findings, the support vector machine model outperforms the others with an accuracy of 76%, with a sensitivity of 0.97, and also a specificity of 0.62 when compared to two other models.

III. METHODOLOGY

We use Visual Studio code in this prediction system, which makes it simple to set up access and distribute.

The voice dataset was downloaded from the UCI Machine Learning repository. This dataset includes 31 persons with Parkinson's disease, 23 of whom had biological voice measures (PD). Each table row relates to 195 recordings which is made by these attributes, and each column contains a distinct voice measurements. The **status** field is set to 0 for healthy persons and 1 for persons having disease, in order to differentiate healthy persons from those with unhealthy person.

The Attribute Information is as follows:

name,MDVP:Fo(Hz),MDVP:Fhi(Hz),MDVP:Flo(Hz),MMDVP:Jitter(Abs),MDVP:RAP,MDVP:PPQ,DVP:Jitter(percent),MDVP:Jitter(percent),MDVP:RAP,MDVP:PPQJitter:DDP,MDVP:Shimmer,MDVP:Shimmer(dB),Shimmer:APQ3,Shimmer:APQ5,MDVP:APQ,Shimmer:DDA,NHR,HNR,status,RPDE,DFA,spread1,spread2,D2,PPE.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

The main stage in predicting parkinson's disease is to construct a model.

Here XGBoost algorithm is used to predict the accuracy and an application is created to predict whether the person that having disease or not based on the dataset recorded on different attributes.

1. Import the packages you'll need.

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings('ignore')
pd.set_option('display.max_columns', None)
pd.set_option('display.max_rows', None)
```

2..Read dataset for training

```
import pandas as pd
data = pd.read_csv('data.csv')
```

3..Import XGBoost Classifier.

```
from xgboost import XGBClassifier
model = XGBClassifier().fit(X_train, y_train)
```

4. Accuracy of Xgboost algorithm.

```
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, f1_score

accuracy_score(y_test, predictions)

0.8974358974358975
```

5. Predict parkinson's using app.

V. RESULT

This section contains the result of experiment, and have predicted the person that having Parkinson's disease using XGBoost algorithm. This app predicts if the given person has disease or not based on the voice dataset information's. And also by processing the algorithm ,the predicted accuracy is 0.897. Based on the dataset we got the following output:

VI. CONCLUSION

The machine learning algorithm XGBoost is used in our implementation to predict Parkinson illness. The accuracy of the train and test data is the same. A single voice recording instance is represented by each row in the CSV file.

VII. REFERENCE

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